

VRE4EIC CATALOG (HORIZON 2020 DMP)

1. DATA SUMMARY

Provide a summary of the data addressing the following issues:

- **State the purpose of the data collection/generation**
- **Explain the relation to the objectives of the project**
- **Specify the types and formats of data generated/collected**
- **Specify if existing data is being re-used (if any)**
- **Specify the origin of the data**
- **State the expected size of the data (if known)**
- **Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful**

The VRE4EIC Metadata Catalog is based upon metadata harvested from RIs and transformed to the canonical rich format. The catalog is essential for the operation of the software components of the VRE - allowing users to access data (and other assets) of the RIs supported by the VRE.

2. FAIR DATA

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

- **Outline the discoverability of data (metadata provision)**
- **Outline the identifiability of data and refer to standard identification mechanism. Do you make use of persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers?**
- **Outline naming conventions used**
- **Outline the approach towards search keyword**
- **Outline the approach for clear versioning**
- **Specify standards for metadata creation (if any). If there are no standards in your discipline describe what metadata will be created and how**

The catalog is metadata hence discoverable; it is meant to assist discovery of assets across multiple heterogeneous RIs represented by their catalogs.

The identifiers used are permanent and unique and complement (federated identifiers) whatever system is used in each RI

The naming conventions follow the CERIF specification

Search keywords may be related to lexical strings in the text fields within the metadata.

CERIF provides facilities for ontologies (with multilinguality and crosswalks) which may be populated if the RI metadata supports this.

Versioning of metadata records is managed with provenance in CERIF. Versions of the catalog are self-described within CERIF.

Metadata collection is by harvesting from the RIs using OAI-PMH and the payload is the richest content available from RI catalogs.

2.2 Making data openly accessible:

- **Specify which data will be made openly available? If some data is kept closed provide rationale for doing so**
- **Specify how the data will be made available**
- **Specify what methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?**
- **Specify where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited**
- **Specify how access will be provided in case there are any restrictions**

All records in the metadata catalog are openly available. The assets to which they refer may have access conditions - recorded in the metadata.

The metadata catalog is made available through the VRE4EIC software components including APIs and user interface utilising data from the catalog which includes not only descriptive metadata but also metadata concerning access rights and obligations.

The metadata catalog is accessed through relational database operators which are triggered by user input to the GUI and/or APIs invoking web services.

The live metadata catalog is stored within the CLOUD service at CNR with a long-term archived copy (updated) at TU Datazentrum. The original data assets recorded as metadata in the catalog reside in the RIs under their DMPs.

The software and catalog are stored at CNR. The catalog also at TU Datazentrum. There are (at present) no access restrictions to the metadata.

2.3 Making data interoperable:

- **Assess the interoperability of your data. Specify what data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies you will follow to facilitate interoperability.**
- **Specify whether you will be using standard vocabulary for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability? If not, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?**

The VRE4EIC catalog is interoperable with the most common metadata standards used by the RIs; typically DC, DCAT, ISO19115, CKAN.

CERIF is continuously updating the ontology of terminology in line with the terms harvested from the RI catalogs

2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses):

- **Specify how the data will be licenced to permit the widest reuse possible**
- **Specify when the data will be made available for re-use. If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed**
- **Specify whether the data produced and/or used in the project is useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why**
- **Describe data quality assurance processes**
- **Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable**

The catalog will be licenced under CC-BY

The metadata catalog will be available for re-use from September 2018

The metadata catalog will be sustained after the end of the project by CNR

The catalog relies on the data quality processes of the RIs since they have management control.

It is intended that the catalog is maintained reusable until replaced by a superior product.

3. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

Explain the allocation of resources, addressing the following issues:

- **Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR. Describe how you intend to cover these costs**
- **Clearly identify responsibilities for data management in your project**
- **Describe costs and potential value of long term preservation**

The costs are difficult to estimate since it depends on the quality and quantity of the RI catalog data harvested. The effort is resourced from the VR4EIC project and additional contributions from partners.

The metadata catalog itself is managed by several partners working together (for resilience)

The cost of long-term preservation is in two parts: maintaining the catalog as is at the end of the project and secondly continued updating. The project is discussing the latter.

4. DATA SECURITY

Address data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data

Access to the metadata catalog is by authorised users using conventional AAAI. Security and privacy of the data (and other) assets is the responsibility of the RIs

declaring their conditions to the VRE4EIC catalog.
Recovery is through the CLOUD standard mechanisms at CNR.

5. ETHICAL ASPECTS

To be covered in the context of the ethics review, ethics section of DoA and ethics deliverables. Include references and related technical aspects if not covered by the former

The catalog ensures access restrictions on ethical grounds to RI data (and other) assets are recorded. There are no ethical considerations for the catalog itself.

6. OTHER

Refer to other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management that you are using (if any)

The data management plans of the RIs determine what is provided to the VRE4EIC catalog